

A Graph Theoretic Approach to Assess Quality of Data for Classification Task

Payel Sadhukhan

Department of Computer Science and Engineering (IoT)
Techno Main, Salt Lake, WB, India

Samrat Gupta*

Information Systems Area, Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad, India
University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia
University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway
samratg@iima.ac.in

Abstract

The correctness of predictions rendered by an AI/ML model is key to its acceptability. To foster researchers' and practitioners' confidence in the model, it is necessary to render an intuitive understanding of the workings of a model. In this work, we attempt to explain a model's working by providing some insights into the quality of data. While doing this, it is essential to consider that revealing the training data to the users is not feasible for logistical and security reasons. However, sharing some interpretable parameters of the training data and correlating them with the model's performance can be helpful in this regard. To this end, we propose a new measure based on Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree (EMST) for quantifying the intrinsic separation (or overlaps) between the data classes. For experiments, we use datasets from diverse domains such as finance, medical, and marketing. We use state-of-the-art measure known as *Davies Bouldin Index (DBI)* to validate our approach on four different datasets from aforementioned domains. The experimental results of this study establish the viability of the proposed approach in explaining the working and efficiency of a classifier. Firstly, the proposed measure of class-overlap quantification has shown a better correlation with the classification performance as compared to DBI scores. Secondly, the results on multi-class datasets demonstrate that the proposed measure can be used to determine the feature importance so as to learn a better classification model.

Keywords – data quality, classification, graph theory, data marketplace, feature importance

1 Introduction

The ever-lasting human urge to render their decision-making capabilities to a machine has resulted in significant advances in artificial intelligence and machine learning (Pomerol, 1997; George et al., 2016). *Automated decision making* – a natural extension of this development has emerged as an important area of research and practice. The hardware and software competencies associated with the operation of a model are improving

^{0*} Corresponding Author

25 with each passing day. This has enabled the models to handle data dimensions beyond normal human per-
26 ception. However, this phenomenon often creates an opacity in the model’s operation for the users receiving
27 the service (Stahl et al., 2021). Additionally, it has been observed that in some cases, semantically incorrect
28 or irrelevant reasoning drove the decisions of a computationally efficient model (Samek and Müller, 2019). It
29 is found that the useful revelations from a given data are often camouflaged with the irrelevant ones (Smith,
30 2020). This calls for an increasing need for an understanding of the quality of data and the working of the
31 automated decision-making models (Rai, 2020; Rudin, 2019).

32 An automated decision-making model is built or crafted on the training data (*training phase*) wherein the
33 model’s task is to predict an unseen test data from the learning of the *training phase*. We may note that
34 we can *understand, explain, or interpret* a model through the data on which it is trained. Following this
35 line of thought, we argue that we can evaluate the efficiency of a model by interpreting the intrinsic class
36 separations (or class overlaps) of the data on which it is trained.

37 To this end, we pose the following research questions:

38 ***RQ1: Can we understand the outcomes of a model by assessing the quality of the data on***
39 ***which it is trained?***

40 In this research, we work on intuiting the modus operandi of a model by exploring the training data. The key
41 element of our exploration is the recognition and quantification of the overlaps of the categories (or classes)
42 in the data and correlating them with the predictive power of the model. There are usually two or more
43 classes in a dataset, and we work on perceiving (quantitatively) the separations (or overlaps) between the
44 classes that exist in the dataset. An efficient model can be built from data that has well-separated classes as
45 compared to the one with overlapping classes (Santos et al., 2022). For example, we can succeed in building
46 a model to distinguish between *fraudulent* and *authentic* bank transactions, if the sets of fraudulent and
47 authentic transactions differ from each other in several characteristics (well separated from each other). In
48 this work, we determine the overlap (or separation) in the training data so as to help the developers build
49 better models and users in explaining the working and performance of a model. In doing so, we propose
50 a Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree (EMST) based novel measure to quantify the class-overlap intrinsic
51 to a dataset. We have formulated the design of this measure on the basis of two key aspects. First, we
52 convert the set of points in a dataset into a connected graph by constructing their EMST. Subsequently,
53 the proportion of homogeneous edges and heterogeneous edges in the transformed graph, and the weights of
54 the homogeneous and the heterogeneous edges. We also use the Davies Bouldin Index (DBI), a popular and
55 existing measure used in the field of data clustering for the purpose of benchmarking (Petrovic, 2006).

56 A model trained on the dataset having overlapping classes (has regions where points from two or more distinct
57 classes co-exist), will have difficulty in classifying points which lie in the overlapped regions. In this work,
58 the *EMST Overlap Index* (EMSTOI) and DBI of a set of datapoints are used to estimate the separations of
59 the intrinsic classes present in it. Usually, a dataset with well-separated classes will possess lower EMSTOI
60 and lower DBI than the one with overlapping classes. This information on intrinsic class separations in the
61 training data can be shared with the practitioners, developers, and users of the model (trained on this data).
62 A lower EMSTOI or DBI (indicating lesser class overlap) can foster the users’ confidence in the outcomes
63 and predictions of the model. It can also help them in distinguishing instrumental features from the less
64 expressive ones. Further, it can help the users, practitioners, and developers in handling critical data types
65 like imbalanced data (Maldonado et al., 2022; Haixiang et al., 2017). Sharing this information is a better
66 option (as compared to sharing the raw and original data with the users) in terms of logistics as well as
67 privacy and integrity.

68 We conduct experimental studies to explore class overlap in datasets originating from diverse domains:

69 In the first study, we used the overlap information obtained from EMSTOI and DBI to ascertain the quality
70 of balanced datasets. We conduct experimental studies on datasets from finance domain. The first dataset
71 in this category known as PaySim is a dataset related to credit card transactions, while the second dataset
72 referred as BankSim is related to the authenticity of bank transactions. These are heavily class-imbalanced
73 synthetic datasets consisting of fraudulent and authentic transactions. We undersample the majority class

74 (set of authentic transactions) to get balanced datasets. We repeat this process several times. We estimate
75 the class separations in the balanced sets and show that in both cases, classifiers render superior performance
76 when the EMSTOI or DBI in the balanced set is low, wherein the proposed EMSTOI is superior to DBI. This
77 establishes the utility of the proposed EMSTOI in assessing the quality of data and subsequently in explaining
78 the model. As a part of this study, we conducted two more experiments to study the relationship between the
79 average amount saved by detecting the fraudulent transactions and class overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI)
80 and the average amount lost by missing the detection of fraudulent transactions and class overlap indices
81 (EMSTOI and DBI). We observed a negative correlation between the average amount saved by fraudulent
82 transaction detection with EMSTOI and DBI. More amount was saved when the classifier was trained on
83 data with well-separated classes (low EMSTOI and DBI). It was further seen that more amount was lost
84 (by missing the detection of fraudulent transactions) when the model was trained on data with overlapping
85 classes (high EMSTOI and DBI).

86 In the second study, we determine feature importance using the EMSTOI and DBI, followed by the incor-
87 poration of computed weights into the classifier modeling, wherein this augmentation improved the learning
88 of the classifier. First, we consider a multi-class dataset from medical domain which pertains to maternal
89 health. In this dataset each data point contains information on the age and five clinical parameters of
90 pregnant women. Second, we consider multi-class dataset originating from marketing domain. This dataset
91 reports the advertising expenditure on different media such as television, radio, and newspaper. We explore
92 the importance of each of the features of these datasets through their EMSTOI and DBI. We trained several
93 classifiers, each modeled and dedicated to a single feature. The performance of the dedicated classifiers is
94 correlated with the EMSTOI and DBI of the individual features. The lower the EMSTOI and DBI for a
95 feature, the better the classification accuracy. This motivated us to conduct another set of experiments
96 where we build an enhanced model incorporating the feature importance. The classification performance of
97 the enhanced model was superior to that of the base model.

98 The two aforementioned studies demonstrate that the developers, practitioners, and users of a model can
99 use the EMSTOI and DBI of training data to understand and explain the workings of a model. These
100 scores are one-dimensional information which can be shared without logistic or privacy concerns. Another
101 advantage of the proposed approach is its model agnostic understanding based on the training data. The
102 proposed EMSTOI can find utility in data marketplaces where the similarity among datasets needs to be
103 derived for enabling functionalities such as data valuation and revenue allocation (Spiekermann, 2019; Zhang
104 et al., 2023). EMSTOI can contribute to quantifying the intrinsic characteristics of datasets to derive their
105 value for machine learning tasks. A data set that has low overlap (in terms of EMSTOI) has a potential to
106 train a better model and can be more valuable for a buyer in the prediction of business outcomes. Class
107 overlap which is an intrinsic characteristic of a dataset (and can be measured through EMSTOI) can be
108 combined with its extrinsic characteristics such as environmental sustainability and perceived uniqueness to
109 recommend its price to the seller while publishing the dataset on a data marketplace.

110 The contributions of this work are as follows:

- 111 • We propose an approach to understand the working of a model by exploring data quality. This
112 investigation is performed in the pre-modeling phase and the learning does not depend on the type of
113 classifier model. Such an approach offers an advantage over other feature-explainability approaches
114 (Ribeiro et al., 2016; Moradi and Samwald, 2021; Lundberg and Lee, 2017) which generate the
115 explanation after the prediction phase only.
- 116 • We design a novel measure based on the Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree (EMST) to recognize
117 and quantify the degree of class overlap in a dataset. We benchmark the proposed measure with
118 DBI, a popular existing measure in the domain of data clustering. The proposed measure named as
119 EMSTOI outperforms state-of-the-art DBI.
- 120 • The proposed approach can be utilized to learn the feature importance as well as the overall quality
121 of the training data. The working efficiency of a model can be explained through this information.

- Experimental studies demonstrate that the proposed EMSTOI can uncover many industry-oriented aspects, such as the amount of money saved by detecting fraudulent transactions, the amount of money lost by missing the detection of fraudulent transactions, and developing an enhanced classifier by incorporating the learned feature importance.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. In the next section, we discuss the extant work on model explainability and data quality. The proposed approach is presented in the following section. The subsequent section outlines the experimental setup of this study. The results of the experimental analysis are presented next. Following this, we discuss the theoretical and managerial implications as well as the limitations of this study. Finally, we conclude this work.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Explainability of Data-Driven Models

In the past decade, AI-based data-driven models have been increasingly used in industries such as finance and banking (Dushimimana et al., 2020; Sánchez et al., 2022), recruitment and selection in education (Ore and Sposato, 2022), resource utilization in healthcare (Topuz et al., 2023). These models have also been applied to prevent the spread of misinformation (Ghai et al., 2024), improve the resilience of supply chains (Zamani et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024), and enhance business outcomes of movies (Gupta et al., 2016b). This remarkable upsurge of AI has given rise to a follow-up question of how to explain the decisions provided by the automated systems (Delgado-Panadero et al., 2022).

To understand the causation leading to the emergence of explainability of data-driven models, we need to briefly recapitulate the timeline of AI developments over the past few decades. The initial years of development in the field of AI (1950-1960) were characterized by rule-based learning systems which were easy to interpret but had low accuracy and predictive power thus limiting their utility (McCarthy et al., 2006). In 1980s researchers began focusing on improving the predictive powers of AI models (Rumelhart et al., 1986). This led to the emergence of statistical learning methods popularly known as Machine Learning (Vapnik, 1999). Subsequently, in 1990s and early 2000s, betterment in accuracy was further achieved by more complex models which were based on artificial neural networks and ensemble methods (Breiman, 2001; LeCun et al., 1998). However, this progression came with a cost wherein as the performance quality of the models increased, the working of the models became increasingly murky and non-explainable to the users (Lipton, 2018). For instance, a neural-network based model for distinguishing husky images and wolves images delivered commendable accuracy on the task, but the model only captured and provided outcome on the basis of background snow instead of the characteristic difference of the two animals (San Kim and Sohn, 2020). Additionally, the quantitative role of prior information in data leads to some bias in the decision-making rationale of a system (DeBrusk, 2018). Hence, data-driven explainability comes with substantial new challenges and opportunities (Adadi and Berrada, 2018; Yang et al., 2022).

One approach for providing of a data-driven model operates on a post-hoc basis. This approach evaluates the explainability of a model on the basis of the predictions from the model. Post-hoc explainability approaches are also used to decipher the modus operandi of an opaque model by the use of rules (Vilone and Longo, 2021; Confalonieri et al., 2021), anchors (Ribeiro et al., 2018) and surrogates (Nóbrega and Marinho, 2019; Ten Broeke et al., 2021). Partial Dependence Plots (PDP) (Greenwell, 2017), Accumulated Local Effect (ALE) Plots (Apley and Zhu, 2016) and Individual Conditional Expectations (ICE) (Goldstein et al., 2015) constitute this class of approach. There is another approach for explaining the predictions wherein specific methods explain the role of the features to arrive at a decision. Some examples of such specific methods are LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016), and SHAP (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). There are several other approaches to explain the features such as, analyzing the performance after permutation of features (Hassan et al., 2021), and counterfactual explanations of the decisions (Wachter et al., 2017; Karimi et al., 2020).

168 The output rendered by a model not only depends on the input which is being fed but also on the data
169 on which it has been trained. Following this line of reasoning, we focus on understanding the data which
170 trains the model providing an ante-hoc explanation of the decisions to be taken by a model. Usually, some
171 intrinsic characteristics of a dataset such as, dispersion, separability, and class imbalance can affect the
172 goodness and working of a model. From a technical perspective, diverse models such as Decision Trees,
173 Support Vector Machines, Neural Network and Nearest Neighbor-based Classifiers have different modus
174 operandi and can operate differently on the same training dataset. However, a part of this training could
175 be attributed to the quality of the training data. Consequently, knowledge of the dataset can provide us
176 considerable insights into the working of different models. Hence, in addition to the explainability of data-
177 driven models, the practitioners are often posed with the challenge of choosing the right data for a task.
178 A few works in literature address similar and related concerns. For example, (Geng and Hamilton, 2007)
179 looks for interesting aspects to be explored in a data mining task, (Gaillard et al., 2010) focuses on finding
180 the right metric to bring out information and (Mao et al., 2019) resorts to domain-guided questionnaire to
181 obtain the right kind of data.

182 Now, we discuss the utility of a popular index which quantifies the separation between the collections of
183 points present in a feature space. In machine learning, clustering is a popular methodology for grouping the
184 data points where similar points are added into the same group while dissimilar points belong to different
185 groups (Jain, 2010). Several popular measures exist, which estimate the goodness of the clustering task
186 (Amigó et al., 2009; Gupta et al., 2016a; Gupta and Kumar, 2020). One such measure is DBI (Petrovic,
187 2006). Though it has been a popular choice and extensively used for evaluating the goodness of clustering
188 output, we didn't find an extant work where it has been used to evaluate the separation of a set of data-points
189 belonging to different classes. This approach of evaluation can be used for a given set of data-points and we
190 use this line of action in our work. The lesser the value of DBI obtained in a task, the more is the separation
191 among the classes.

192 In this work, we demonstrate the use of DBI to estimate the intrinsic separations existing between the
193 classes present in the training data. While computing DBI for the training data, we assume that it is
194 a collection of c distinct classes. The computation of DBI is dependent on the similarities between the
195 points arising from different classes. For each class i , $1 \leq i \leq c$, the computation of DBI involves finding
196 out quantitative value of its similarity with another class j , $1 \leq j \leq c$, $j \neq i$. DBI is the cumulative
197 sum of such quantitative similarities overall i , that is for all the classes. The mathematical definition and
198 formulation of DBI is provided in Appendix 8.1. For a model which is assigned with the task of classifying
199 the data-points, it is desirable that the classes in the training data should be distinct from each other. In
200 mathematical terminology, the different categories should originate from distributions with highly different
201 population means (Kukar and Kononenko, 2002) thus resulting in a low DBI. The minimum value of DBI is
202 *zero* and denotes the ideal scenario of maximum separation between the categories. However, DBI provides
203 overlap quantification under several stringent assumptions such as the classes should possess disparate cluster
204 centers. As such, DBI cannot be relied upon to perceive the proportion of class overlap in a dataset.
205 Hence, we need a more generalized index to quantify class overlaps while providing better explainability
206 into the goodness of a dataset. Leveraging this gap in the research we propose a new measure based on
207 the Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree for quantifying the class overlaps in the training data. Since data
208 quality particularly in classification tasks is a function of intrinsic characteristics of a dataset it is important
209 to investigate class overlap in a dataset. The objective of this study is to investigate how the working of a
210 model can be explained without generating the model itself such that the explanation is model-agnostic. This
211 is based on the intuition that training data that has good intrinsic separation of its classes will result in the
212 implementation of an efficient classifier. On the contrary, training data with overlapping classes will generate
213 a sub-optimal classifier (Vuttipittayamongkol et al., 2021). In order to validate our premise, we correlate
214 quantified class overlap indices with the predictions of different models. In doing so, we also benchmark the
215 proposed EMSTOI with state-of-the-art DBI to determine the intrinsic overlaps in the training data.

3 Proposed Research Methodology

217 An insight into the overlap of data-points in the training data can explain the impending classification
 218 performance by determining the goodness of the undersampled dataset as well as feature importance. We
 219 work towards this objective and propose a novel measure to quantify the class overlaps in a dataset. As
 220 mentioned in section 2.2, the new measure overcomes the limitations of state-of-the-art DBI. DBI can provide
 221 information about class overlap only when the classes originate from distinct clusters. It can provide a
 222 sub-optimal output when the origin of the classes in a dataset overlaps. We quantify and compute the
 223 separations intrinsic to a dataset by using the proposed EMSTOI and DBI in the pre-modeling phase. In the
 224 post-modeling phase, we obtain the classes of a set of unknown test points from the model and compute the
 225 classification performance (accuracy and F_1). Subsequently, we compute the correlation between the class
 226 overlap scores and classification performance with an expectation that higher separations between the classes
 227 present in a dataset (lower class overlap index) will be positively correlated with classification performance.

228 3.1 A new measure based on minimum spanning tree

229 We use Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree (EMST) based approach to form a connected network from a
 230 given set of datapoints. An EMST of a finite set of n points in a feature space connects them by a set of
 231 $n - 1$ line segments where the points serve as the endpoints, minimizing the total length of the segments.
 232 The technical foundation of EMST is provided in Appendix 8.2. It is important to note that, each of the
 233 n points can belong to any one of the given classes. After forming the EMST, we look at each edge. If
 234 both the vertices of an edge belong to the same class, we call it a *homogeneous edge*. If the vertices of
 235 an edge belong to different classes, we call it a *heterogeneous edge*. The percentage of heterogeneous edges
 236 in an EMST indicate the degree of class overlap in a given dataset. Further, the average weights of the
 237 homogeneous edges and the heterogeneous edges also provide insight into the class overlaps. In a dataset
 238 with low-class overlap, each class will be tight-knit resulting in low average homogeneous edge weights and
 239 a higher value for average heterogeneous edge weight. We employ a ratio of the number of heterogeneous
 240 edges over the number of homogeneous edges, and ratio of the average weight of homogeneous edges over
 241 the average weight of heterogeneous edges to quantify the overlap of the classes present in a dataset. We
 242 define the EMST-based class-overlap of a given dataset \mathcal{D} denoted by EMSTO as follows:

$$\text{EMSTO} = \frac{\varepsilon_{hom}}{\varepsilon_{het}} \times \frac{\nu_{het}}{\nu_{hom}} \quad (1)$$

243 where ε_{hom} and ε_{het} denote the average homogeneous edge weight and average heterogeneous edge weight
 244 respectively. ν_{hom} and ν_{het} denote the number of homogeneous edges and the number of heterogeneous edges
 245 in the EMST of the given dataset. The technical details of the proposed equation are detailed in Appendix
 246 8.3. The more the number of heterogeneous edges, the more is overlap between the classes. Additionally,
 247 smaller homogeneous edge weights (shorter homogeneous edges) indicate compact class structures. A low-
 248 class overlap wherein homogeneous edges have lower weights than the heterogeneous edges is desirable as the
 249 classes therein are separated from each other and it is expected that the models trained on such a dataset
 250 would deliver efficient performance. Thus, we compute and explain the class separations intrinsic to a dataset
 251 and, consequently, to the model. The values of EMSTO can range from 0 to ∞ . The former indicates no
 252 overlap while the latter is obtained when the classes originate from identical distribution. When we want to
 253 compare two distributions, such diverse range of values can be too abstract. To address this shortcoming,
 254 we tweak the EMSTO value mathematically in the following manner to compute EMST based class overlap
 255 index (EMSTOI). Similar to DBI, this index quantifies the overlap in a dataset in a more effective way.

$$\text{EMSTOI} = \frac{\text{EMSTO}}{\text{EMSTO} + 1} \quad (2)$$

256 Unlike EMSTO, the range of EMSTOI is bounded in $[0, 1]$. The higher the overlap, the higher the value
 257 of EMSTOI. The mathematical properties of EMSTOI are discussed in Appendix 8.4. Figure 1 shows the
 258 variation of EMSTOI and DBI in differently overlapped datasets. In each sub-figure of Figure 1, we have

259 constructed a synthetic 2-class dataset where the points belong to exactly one of the two given classes
260 (indicated by blue and orange colors). For a scenario wherein each class originates from a single cluster,
261 both EMSTOI and DBI have shown strong correlations with the degree of overlap. The values of both
262 measures have increased with the increase in the class overlap.

263 However, in situations where each class originates from multiple clusters, DBI can fail to correctly capture
264 the overlap in the data. The issue happens when the cluster centers of different classes are located within
265 a small vicinity. The technical details can be found in Appendix 8.1. Figure 2 shows four dataset in which
266 each class originates from two or more non-overlapping clusters. Consequently, the classes in each dataset
267 are well-separated. In all the cases, EMSTOI scores are approximately 0, and it is in congruence with the
268 actual scenario as there is a low overlap between the classes. On the contrary, the value of DBI is quite
269 high, spuriously indicating a strong overlap between the classes. This anomaly in the DBI arises because the
270 resultant means (cluster centers) for the two classes are collocated thus misguiding the DBI computation.
271 The proposed measure EMSTOI is immune to such variations and can render correct indications about the
272 class overlap present in the data.

273 3.2 Addressing the class imbalance problem

274 Class-imbalance problem is a conspicuous characteristic of data arising from a number of real-world domains
275 (Khushi et al., 2021; Lucas and Jurgovsky, 2020). The learning of models gets severely plagued due to this
276 issue (Johnson and Khoshgoftaar, 2019). Researchers and practitioners often work on balancing the classes
277 of imbalanced datasets. The most popular and convenient way to balance a dataset is *undersampling* which
278 means eliminating the points from the majority class. However, undersampling can be effective only if it
279 provides a separation of the classes.

280 Therefore, we assess and explain the quality of an undersampled dataset by measuring its class overlap
281 through EMSTOI and DBI. For validation, we generate several sets of undersampled datasets from a class-
282 imbalanced dataset. We compute the classification performances across all the undersampled sets and explore
283 the correlation between overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI) and classification performances. Empirically,
284 we expect a negative correlation between the overlap indices and classification performances.

285 3.3 Explaining and augmenting the features

286 We assume that there are d features and n points in a dataset, \mathcal{D} . We compute EMSTOI and DBI value d
287 times, once for each feature. A feature that gives lesser EMSTOI and DBI has a better class-distinguishing
288 ability and it plays a more instrumental role in the operation of the classifier model. For example, let there
289 be two features f_i and f_j in \mathcal{D} , and their class overlap indices be \mathcal{O}_{f_i} and \mathcal{O}_{f_j} respectively. If $\mathcal{O}_{f_j} < \mathcal{O}_{f_i}$ and
290 also differs by a considerable amount, we can say that feature f_j is a better distinguisher for the two classes
291 than f_i . When the feature values are different for different classes, it can be effective in distinguishing the
292 classes. So investigating the class overlaps in the individual features can provide explainability. However,
293 the class overlap scores do not reveal anything about the ranges of the feature values. Without looking at
294 the individual values of f_i and f_j for the data points, we can get an understanding of the intrinsic class
295 overlaps using the EMSTOI and DBI values.

296 We further explore the correlations between these scores and the classification performances of the features.
297 EMSTOI and DBI are low when we have well-separated classes in a dataset. A feature f_j which possesses non-
298 overlapping ranges of values for different classes will possess low EMSTOI and DBI than another feature f_i
299 with overlapping ranges. By virtue of the separations in the feature ranges, f_j will train an efficient classifier
300 model, M_j (say) which can give a competent performance score. On the other hand, f_i with overlapping
301 feature ranges for different classes is likely to output a higher overlap index. Let the classifier model trained
302 by f_i be denoted by M_i . Consequently, f_i will train a less competent classifier model. On the same set of
303 query points, we can expect the accuracy of M_i to be lesser than that of M_j . We will conduct our experiments

(a) Low overlap,
EMSTOI=0.003,
DB=0.396

(b) Increased overlap,
EMSTOI=0.052,
DB=0.713

(c) Moderate overlap,
EMSTOI=0.386,
DB=1.709

(d) High overlap,
EMSTOI=0.497,
DB=178.183

Figure 1: A comparison of EMSTOI and DBI for quantifying the overlaps in a dataset with two classes wherein each class has exactly one cluster.

304 on datasets from real-world domains to explore and validate this premise. We can also employ the notion of
 305 class overlap to determine the feature importance. The feature which has the lowest class overlap is the one
 306 with the highest feature importance by virtue of rendering the best possible separation of the classes. We
 307 operationalize this and compute the feature importance from the class-overlap scores which are computed
 308 through the proposed EMSTO and DBI.

309 We assume that there are d features in a dataset \mathcal{D} , denoted by f_1, f_2, \dots, f_d . Let $\mathcal{O}_{f_1}, \mathcal{O}_{f_2}, \dots, \mathcal{O}_{f_d}$ be
 310 class-overlap indices of f_1, f_2, \dots, f_d respectively. Let us denote the importance of feature f_i , $1 \leq i \leq d$ by
 311 FI_i . We compute this value from $\mathcal{O}_{f_1}, \mathcal{O}_{f_2}, \dots, \mathcal{O}_{f_d}$ as follows.

$$FI_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^d \mathcal{O}_{f_i}}{\mathcal{O}_{f_i}} \quad (3)$$

312 Equation (3) signifies that FI_i is inversely proportional to the class-overlap scores, \mathcal{O}_{f_i} . Lesser the value of

(a) 2 classes,
EMSTOI=0.0001,
DBI=1319.267

(b) 3 classes,
EMSTOI=0.0001,
DBI=867.093

(c) 4 classes,
EMSTOI=0.0001,
DBI=858.180

(d) 4 classes,
EMSTOI=0.0001,
DBI=713.185

Figure 2: Comparison of EMSTOI scores and DBI in binary and multi-class synthetic datasets. In Figures (a), (b) and (c), the points belonging to a class originate from exactly two clusters (and are given a distinct color). In Figure (d), the points belonging to three classes (red, orange and blue) originate from two clusters and green originates from three clusters. In all four scenarios, the mean (resultant cluster centers) of the classes coincides in the centre of the feature space. We may note that the clusters are well separated from each other, resulting in non-overlap of the classes. This is well indicated by EMSTOI which are approximately 0 in all four cases. However, DBI are high in all four cases spuriously indicating a considerable overlap in the data. This shows the robustness and advantage of EMSTOI over DBI in quantifying the overlap in the data.

313 \mathcal{O}_{f_i} (less overlap of the classes using that feature) of f_i , the more the feature importance. It further indicates
 314 that if the \mathcal{O}_{f_i} values are equal for $1 \leq i \leq d$, the feature importance values will be equal for all the features.
 315 The computed feature importance score depends on the EMSTOI and DBI of the concerned feature as well
 316 as all other features.

317 4 Experimental setup

318 We have conducted two experimental studies to have a pre-modelling understanding of the quality of datasets
 319 (that train different models). The first study is focused on the overlap of the minority and majority classes
 320 while the second study focuses on investigation of feature importances in a dataset. We use a variety of
 321 datasets for experiments pertaining to these studies.

322 4.1 Datasets

323 For the first study, we use two synthetic datasets from the finance domain, namely *PaySim* and *BankSim*.
324 *PaySim* dataset is constructed by simulating mobile money transactions on the basis of a sample of real
325 transactions (Lopez-Rojas et al., 2016). These are extracted from one month of financial logs from a mobile
326 money service based in an African country. There are nine numeric and categorical features present in total
327 in the dataset. Out of these, we have considered five numeric features namely amount of transaction, old
328 balance of origin, a new balance of origin, old balance of destination, and new balance of destination for
329 our study. Each transaction is categorized as *authentic* or *fraudulent*. In this dataset, 6,362,620 mobile
330 transactions are present wherein 8,213 are fraudulent thus making it a highly imbalanced dataset.

331 *BankSim* dataset is formed from an agent-based simulator of bank payments (Lopez-Rojas and Axelsson,
332 2014). This simulation is based on a sample of aggregated transactional data provided by a bank in Spain.
333 The main motive for constructing this synthetic data is to provide a dataset for research in the domain of
334 fraud detection. A total of 594,643 transactions are present in this dataset, out of which, 7,200 transactions
335 are fraudulent. Hence, this dataset is also highly imbalanced. In this dataset also, there are nine numeric
336 and categorical features present in total. We have used three numeric features age, gender of the transactor,
337 and amount of transaction for our study. The category of each data point (transaction) is either fraudulent
338 or normal.

339 For the second study, we have used two datasets originating from medical and marketing domains respectively.
340 The first dataset namely *Maternal health* is collected from rural areas of Bangladesh (Ahmed et al., 2020).
341 It has a total of six features - age and five clinical parameters namely systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood
342 pressure, blood sugar level, body temperature, and heart rate. Each of the 1,014 datapoints consists of
343 information on these six parameters for a pregnant woman. The women are categorized with respect to their
344 risks for maternal mortality. Each woman belongs to any one of the following classes - *high risk*, *medium*
345 *risk* or *low risk*.

346 The second dataset known as *Advertising* dataset¹ originates from the marketing domain and deals with the
347 relationship between amounts invested in the marketing of a product through TV, radio, and newspapers
348 (features) and the actual sales outcomes of the product. There are 200 observations in this dataset wherein
349 the outcome of the sale is the dependent variable. Here the outcome of the sales is a continuous dependent
350 variable and we have divided its range into five non-overlapping bins to form a multi-class classification
351 problem.

352 We divide each of these datasets into two mutually exclusive and equal partitions so as to generate the
353 training set and the test set.

354 4.2 Classifiers used for evaluation

355 We have used four classifiers across all of the experiments for evaluation and validation of the proposed
356 approach.

- 357 • **Support Vector Classifier (SVC)** (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995): It is a supervised learning algo-
358 rithm which draws a separating boundary (hyperplane) between the two classes. We have considered
359 a linear model and allowed some tolerance for misclassification by setting the parameter $C = 1$ and
360 $\gamma = 2$. These parameters are related to amount of misclassification allowed during training and
361 curvature of the decision boundary, respectively.
- 362 • **k-Nearest Neighbor Classifier (KNN)** (Cover and Hart, 1967): It is an intuitive and popular
363 classification scheme. Using this classifier, the test points are classified by looking at the classes of
364 their neighboring points. It does not involve any parameter other than the neighborhood size k . In
365 this study, we have set $k = 1$.
- 366 • **Naive Bayes Classifier (NB)** (Domingos and Pazzani, 1997): Naive Bayes Classifier is based on

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/ashydv/advertising-dataset>

367 the Bayes Theorem of the conditional dependence between the features and the classes of the points.
368 A key underlying assumption in this particular classifier is the independence of the features.

369 • **XG-Boost Classifier** (Chen and Guestrin, 2016): It is an ensemble method which is widely used
370 for large datasets, because of its parallelizable nature. XGBoost consists of gradient-boosted decision
371 trees. We have used this classifier in its default settings.

372 4.3 Evaluation criteria

373 We need two sets of criteria, one to measure the classification performance of the data, and the second to
374 measure the correlation between the overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI) and classification performance.
375 For measuring the classification performance, we use *accuracy*, and *minority class F_1* . For computing the
376 correlation between overlap indices and classification performance, we use *Pearson correlation coefficient*
377 and *Spearman's rank correlation coefficient*. More details about these evaluation criteria are provided in
378 Appendix 8.5 and 8.6.

379 4.3.1 Evaluation criteria for classification performance

380 The datasets used in this study are unbalanced. Evaluating the classification performance of such datasets
381 is slightly different from datasets with balanced classes. Accuracy scores give an idea about the overall
382 performance of a dataset. However, considering only the accuracy scores provide only a partial understanding
383 of the imbalanced datasets. Therefore, we have also considered minority class F_1 to evaluate the performance
384 of the class imbalance dataset.

385 4.3.2 Evaluation criteria for measuring the correlation

386 The main contribution of this work is the introduction of EMSTOI, through which we can measure the
387 overlap present in the data in the pre-modeling phase itself. This knowledge is helpful in assessing the
388 quality of the data on which a classification model is trained. We may note that DBI are also indicative of
389 the overlap in the data to some extent however, it works well only when the classes originate from different
390 cluster centers (Appendix 8.1).

391 We compute the correlations between overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI) and classifier performances. Cor-
392 relation refers to the extent of the linear relationship between two variables. The value of correlation, r is
393 $-1 \leq r \leq 1$. If two variables increase or decrease in the same direction, the sign of the correlation is positive.
394 On the contrary, if the decrease of one leads to the increase of another and vice versa (different direction),
395 the sign of the correlation is negative. The magnitude of the correlation value indicates the degree of relation
396 or connection (linearity). The stronger the correlation, the greater the value, and vice versa. A correlation
397 value of $r = 0$ indicates no correlation between the two variables. A r value close to zero (from either side)
398 indicates a low correlation.

399 The two variables in our case are the performance score of the model and the overlap scores of the balanced
400 data. If we obtain a negative correlation of a significant magnitude, we can conclude that our approach
401 is viable. We compute the correlations between performance and overlap scores via two standard metrics
402 *Pearson correlation coefficient* and *Spearman rank correlation coefficient*. The details of these coefficients is
403 provided in Appendix 8.6.

404 5 Results and Analysis

405 In this section, we report the results of the two sets of experiments. In the first study, we utilize the *PaySim*
406 and the *BankSim* datasets. In this study, we investigate the correlation between overlap indices (EMSTOI
407 and DBI) and classification performance followed by the association between overlap indices and the amount

408 of money saved and money lost. Subsequently, the second study is conducted using *Maternal Health* and
 409 *Advertising* datasets where our objective is to ascertain the feature importance through overlap indices.

410 **5.1 Analyzing the correlation between overlap indices and classification performance**

Table 1: Results of correlation of *EMSTOI* and classification performance on *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets

Classifier	PaySim				BankSim			
	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman
	F_1		Accuracy		F_1		Accuracy	
SVC	-0.226	-0.214	-0.255	-0.177	-0.283	-0.242	-0.265	-0.188
KNN	-0.309	-0.287	-0.230	-0.192	-0.251	-0.284	-0.287	-0.269
NB	-0.252	-0.279	-0.301	-0.386	-0.188	-0.257	-0.287	-0.288
XGBoost	-0.179	-0.223	-0.400	-0.389	-0.292	-0.273	-0.202	-0.168

Table 2: Results of correlation between *DBI* and classification performance on *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets

Classifier	PaySim				BankSim			
	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman
	F_1		Accuracy		F_1		Accuracy	
SVC	-0.222	-0.206	-0.227	-0.236	-0.271	-0.142	-0.149	-0.051
KNN	-0.247	-0.252	-0.071	-0.127	-0.165	-0.166	-0.138	-0.127
NB	-0.263	-0.217	-0.223	-0.192	-0.262	-0.217	-0.170	-0.156
XGBoost	-0.267	-0.110	-0.235	-0.174	-0.191	-0.169	-0.134	-0.122

Table 3: Results of correlation between *EMSTOI* and amount lost and amount saved on *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets

Classifier	PaySim				BankSim			
	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman
	Amount lost		Amount saved		Amount lost		Amount saved	
SVC	0.281	0.196	-0.323	-0.282	0.264	0.139	-0.207	-0.183
KNN	0.270	0.265	-0.222	-0.175	0.195	0.236	-0.278	-0.315
NB	0.184	0.215	-0.404	-0.328	0.396	0.257	-0.235	-0.348
XGBoost	0.205	0.245	-0.434	-0.361	0.243	0.132	-0.199	-0.251

411 The objective of the first study is to investigate the correlation between class overlap and classification
 412 performance. The class overlaps in the undersampled datasets are measured through EMSTOI and DBI. We
 413 also evaluate the classification performance of different classifiers trained on the undersampled *PaySim* and
 414 *BankSim* datasets. We report the correlation results in Table 1 and Table 2.

415 For each dataset, there are four classifiers (SVC, KNN, NB, and XGBoost), two performance evaluation
 416 metrics (accuracy and F_1), and two correlation metrics (Person and Spearman) — leading to $(4 \times 2 \times 2 =)$
 417 16 cases. For both *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets, we have repeated this process 50 times (obtaining 50
 418 sets of balanced datasets) and computed the correlation between classification performance (accuracy and
 419 minority class F_1) and the overlap score (EMSTOI and DBI). As shown in Table 1, for both datasets, a weak
 420 negative correlation (value ≤ -0.2) is obtained between EMSTOI and classification performance in 13 out
 421 of 16 cases. These results are in congruence with our expectations and it can be deduced that classification
 422 performances could be explained through the EMSTOI scores. In terms of DBI (Table 2), a weak negative
 423 correlation (Schober et al., 2018) is obtained between DBI and classification performance 11 out of 16 times
 424 on *PaySim* dataset and 3 out of 16 times on *BankSim* dataset. These results demonstrate the superiority of
 425 the EMSTOI in assessing the quality of datasets on which different classifiers are trained.

Table 4: Results of correlation between *DBI* and amount lost, and amount saved on *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets

Classifier	PaySim				BankSim			
	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman	Pearson	Spearman
	Amount lost		Amount saved		Amount lost		Amount saved	
SVC	0.092	0.152	-0.204	0.186	0.143	0.071	-0.212	-0.133
KNN	0.115	0.116	-0.225	-0.249	0.171	0.180	-0.262	-0.317
NB	0.159	0.164	-0.291	-0.262	0.082	0.160	-0.213	-0.163
XGBoost	0.133	0.206	-0.112	-0.133	0.224	0.174	-0.213	-0.221

426 5.2 Analyzing the correlation between overlap indices and the amount of money saved and 427 lost

428 We investigate the correlation between overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI) and the amount saved through the
429 detection of fraudulent transactions. We also investigate the correlation between overlap indices (EMSTOI
430 and DBI) and the amount lost by missing the detection of fraudulent transactions. The results for EMSTOI
431 and DBI are reported in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively.

432 A lesser overlap between the minority class and the majority class of a balanced dataset indicates quality data.
433 This quality data is supposed to learn an efficient classifier model which can detect fraudulent transactions
434 accurately and save more amount of money. On the other hand, an increased overlap of the different
435 classes will train a sub-optimal classifier. Such a model will misclassify the fraudulent transactions and
436 increase the loss incurred. We have looked into these perspectives and computed the average amount saved
437 and lost through the detection of fraudulent transactions and the overlap indices of the balanced datasets.
438 For both *PaySim* and *BankSim* datasets, we have repeated this process 50 times (obtaining 50 sets of
439 balanced datasets) and computed the correlation between the amount saved/lost and the overlap indices.
440 The correlations with the EMSTOI are reported in Table 3 and with DBI are reported in Table 4. As
441 expected both EMSTOI and DBI are positively correlated with the amount lost and negatively correlated
442 with the amount saved on both datasets. It is noteworthy that for the correlation with the amount lost,
443 EMSTOI outperforms DBI (6/8 vs. 1/8) on *PaySim* dataset as well as (5/8 vs. 1/8) on *BankSim* dataset.
444 Similarly, for correlation with the amount saved, EMSTOI performs at par with DBI (7/8 vs. 5/8) on
445 *PaySim* dataset and (6/8 vs. 6/8) on *BankSim* dataset. These results substantiate that EMSTOI can better
446 assess the quality of data used for training a classification model.

447 5.3 Analyzing the feature importance using overlap indices

448 We also study the association between class overlap and classification performance for each individual feature.
449 We report the class overlap indices (EMSTOI and DBI) and the accuracy values obtained through four
450 classifiers (SVM, KNN, NB, and XGBoost) for all the 6 features of *Maternal health* and 3 features of
451 *Advertising* dataset in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively. These results show a strong association between
452 the class-overlap indices of the features and the accuracy of classification.

453 On *Maternal health* dataset, the lowest EMSTOI and DBI are obtained for *Blood Sugar*, and the best
454 classification performance is delivered by this feature on all four classifiers (Table 5). Additionally, in
455 the *Advertising* dataset, the lowest EMSTOI and DBI are obtained for *TV*, and the best classification
456 performance is delivered by this feature on all four classifiers (Table 6). These findings establish the utility
457 of the proposed approach in determining the feature importance by examining the association between
458 feature overlap scores (EMSTOI and DBI) and their respective classification performances. It is important
459 to note that the feature importances obtained by our approach are in the pre-modeling phase and without
460 the intervention of the test phase. Our approach is also model-agnostic and depends only on the training
461 data.

Table 5: Results of feature-specific overlap indices (EMSTOI) and accuracy of *Maternal Health* dataset

Features	Overlap Indices		Classifiers			
	EMSTOI	DBI	SVC	KNN	NB	XG-Boost
Age	0.624	8.116	0.484	0.519	0.479	0.502
Systolic Blood Pressure	0.529	3.511	0.590	0.636	0.618	0.641
Diastolic Blood Pressure	0.609	4.920	0.552	0.558	0.581	0.581
Blood Sugar	0.486	2.557	0.622	0.647	0.645	0.668
Body Temperature	0.633	6.375	0.535	0.539	0.544	0.525
Heart Rate	0.687	15.248	0.464	0.502	0.539	0.567

Table 6: Results of feature-specific overlap indices (EMSTOI) and accuracy of *Advertising* dataset

Features	Overlap Indices		Classifiers			
	EMSTOI	DBI	SVC	KNN	NB	XG-Boost
TV	0.452	3.521	0.540	0.540	0.500	0.500
Radio	0.681	22.418	0.480	0.350	0.340	0.340
Newspaper	0.772	29.283	0.320	0.230	0.280	0.280

Table 7: Classification accuracy obtained on original data, data weighted by *EMSTOI* driven feature importance, and data weighted by *DBI* driven feature importance

	Classifiers			
	SVC	KNN	NB	XG-Boost
Maternal Health				
Original data	0.660	0.582	0.635	0.624
Data weighted by FI-EMSTOI	0.571	0.609	0.651	0.632
Data weighted by FI-DBI	0.566	0.614	0.643	0.637
Advertising				
Original data	0.708	0.740	0.640	0.747
Data weighted by FI-EMSTOI	0.806	0.797	0.650	0.768
Data weighted by FI-DBI	0.736	0.755	0.648	0.762

462 Further, we incorporate the feature importance scores in the data before building the model. Prior to training
 463 the model, we created feature importance-informed training data. This was accomplished by adding weights
 464 to the features in decreasing order of their EMSTOI. We investigated the outcome of this augmentation
 465 on classification performance. We demonstrate this through experiments on *Maternal Health dataset* and
 466 *Advertising* datasets. For these experiments, half of the data points are used in model building, and the
 467 remaining half is used in prediction. The results of over 100 independent runs on four classifiers are reported
 468 in Table 7. It shows that the use of weighted features has offered better performance on three out of four
 469 classifiers on *Maternal Health dataset*. On *Advertisement* dataset, the use of weighted features has improved
 470 the performances across all four classifiers.

471 6 Discussion

472 In this study, we posit that the quality of data is integral to the supervised learning tasks and their business
 473 or financial outcomes. We consider the problem of explaining the performance of a classifier in the pre-
 474 modeling phase by assessing the quality of data. The proposed index EMSTOI offers an advantage in terms
 475 of data induced, model-agnostic understanding of classification performance. The proposed Euclidean mini-
 476 mum spanning tree-based index helps in appropriately measuring class overlaps in data wherein the classes
 477 can originate from single or multiple clusters. It is noteworthy that when classes originate from multiple
 478 clusters, state-of-the-art indices such as DBI may fail to accurately assess the class-overlap. Experiments
 479 and comparative analysis using datasets from a variety of domains demonstrate that the proposed approach

480 yields superior assessment of training data. We transform the data-points into a connected graph by con-
481 structing their Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree. Subsequently, the proposed index captures the ratio of
482 heterogeneous edges over homogeneous edges in an EMST transformed dataset, and the ratio of average
483 weight of homogeneous edges over the average weight of heterogeneous edges thereby helping in quantifying
484 the class overlaps in data wherein classes may originate from multiple clusters.
485 The results of classification are not only based on the characteristics of the model but also on the data which
486 is used to learn the model. Therefore, the examination of data can provide insights in explaining the output
487 of a model. Our experimental analysis shows that there is indeed a correlation between class overlap and
488 classification performance wherein EMSTOI is better correlated (as compared to DBI) with classification
489 accuracy as well as minority class F1 scores. EMSTOI also correlates better with the amount saved or lost by
490 detecting fraudulent transactions in terms of both correlation coefficients namely Pearson correlation coeffi-
491 cient and Spearman rank correlation coefficient. Further, the overlap indices can also be used to derive the
492 importance of different features and classification performance based on each feature. Thus using data from
493 diverse domains, we analyze and demonstrate the viability of the proposed approach. The use of EMSTOI
494 in comparison to DBI in assessing the quality of data which is used to train classification models represents
495 the key methodological contribution of this study.
496 This study responds to recent call for research to find innovative ways to enhance and understand classifi-
497 cation performance thereby helping in the more effective exploration of the search universe (Chhabra et al.,
498 2024). It is important to note that several classification models have been developed and are in use among
499 researchers and practitioners (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995; Cover and Hart, 1967; Domingos and Pazzani, 1997;
500 Chen and Guestrin, 2016). These models demonstrate a wide variety of capabilities depending on the do-
501 main for which they are being used. Through the experimental analysis, we demonstrate that the proposed
502 approach for explaining the classification performance is model as well as domain agnostic. The proposed
503 index will provide an impetus to research in the field of explainable AI for knowledge creation.

504 6.1 Theoretical Implications

505 This study has several theoretical implications. It helps in advancing understanding of how the different
506 features and their meta-characteristics are related to each other, given a dataset related to a particular do-
507 main. This study also suggests that classification performance can be significantly improved by investigating
508 data in the pre-modeling phase, rather than doing one post hoc validation at the end. Such middle-range
509 theorizing is crucial to advance the literature on how emerging AI and ML models can deliver superior
510 business value (Paullada et al., 2021). Deducing explainability through interpretable parameters of the data
511 is a natural progression toward advancements in AI modeling (Decoupes et al., 2024).
512 The proposed approach offers scholars a new way to reason about empirically observed variations in the
513 classification performance of models. The introduction of Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree based ap-
514 proach also offers a systematic way to analyze the geometric properties of data thereby suggesting the need
515 to revisit existing data quality metrics by adopting graph-theoretic principles (Hanauer et al., 2022). This
516 approach can overcome challenges arising in a variety of business environments by allowing stakeholders to
517 gain insights into model behavior without compromising the confidentiality of data.
518 Also, the experimental results demonstrate that the proposed index can discern feature importance more
519 effectively in multi-class datasets. This advances theoretical understanding of how feature spaces can be op-
520 timized for improved classifier performance, thereby offering new feature selection strategies which prioritize
521 intrinsic class separability (Ram et al., 2022). The experimental validation across diverse domains, including
522 finance, medical, and marketing datasets, demonstrate the generalizability of the proposed index for data
523 quality assessment. Future studies can expand upon theoretical implications of this study by exploring
524 additional graph-theoretic artifacts or applying the proposed index in novel contexts such as unsupervised
525 learning or data augmentation. We hope that the insights of this study inspire future research designs to
526 assess the quality of collected data prior to empirically analyzing it using different types of quantitative
527 models.

528 6.2 Managerial Implications

529 In today’s digital environment, there is a lot of heterogeneity in the data generated from a variety of ap-
530 plications (Bendre and Thool, 2016). The business solutions that classification models offer have gained
531 traction as they simplify mundane tasks while enabling organizations to achieve productive results (Tschang
532 and Almirall, 2021). Considering such a scenario, classification models need to accommodate the data with
533 varying structure, characteristics, and quality in an effective way. At the same time, enterprises may like to
534 be able to use interpretable measures of data quality wherein they can ascertain the appropriate classification
535 model for their work. As such, managers can use the proposed index to evaluate the readiness of datasets
536 for classification tasks, ensuring that classification models are built on reliable data.

537 The increasing expectations of customers and the pursuit to improve classification performance are driving
538 researchers to develop new classification approaches without considering the intrinsic characteristics of data
539 (Vuttipittayamongkol et al., 2021). The proposed approach can not only generate significant gains for or-
540 ganizations by offering explainability of classification tasks but also allowing customization of classification
541 models that serve the needs of diverse sets of users. This can help build trust among stakeholders, by demon-
542 strating the logical foundations of model decisions without compromising data security. This is particularly
543 critical for industries dealing with sensitive information, such as healthcare and finance, where compliance
544 with regulations like GDPR or HIPAA is mandatory (Sargiotis, 2024).

545 The ability of the proposed EMSTOI to determine feature importance in multi-class datasets can guide
546 managers in prioritizing data attributes that matter most for predictive accuracy. This targeted focus can
547 streamline data collection processes. Moreover, the proposed index can be used by managers to identify
548 classification challenges early in the machine learning pipeline. Overall, the proposed approach has the po-
549 tential to minimize the risk of deploying underperforming models, reducing financial losses and reputational
550 damage associated with misclassifications.

551 6.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

552 This study is not devoid of limitations. First, the generalizability of the results to unstructured data, such
553 as image, time series, networked data or text datasets remains to be established. Second, the computa-
554 tional complexity for constructing and computing EMSTOI may pose challenges when applied to large-scale
555 datasets with high dimensionality. Third, the reliance on Euclidean distance assumes that data distribu-
556 tions are well represented in Euclidean space. This may limit the method’s effectiveness for data where
557 relationships are better captured by non-Euclidean distance measures (Abedi, 2021) Finally, the offline ex-
558 perimentation performed in this study cannot completely replace online real-time experimentation. As a
559 result, the offline laboratory experimental approach used in this work has inherent limitations. Nonetheless,
560 we believe that this study will guide future research and add rigor to the field of data quality assessment for
561 AI modelling.

562 Future research studies in the area of data quality assessment can focus on exploring how the proposed
563 approach performs for unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement learning environments. Secondly,
564 future studies could focus on integrating the proposed index with automated feature selection algorithms to
565 optimize dataset quality and improve model training. Thirdly, since we use only DBI as a benchmark in this
566 study, future studies should validate the proposed index against a wider array of existing measures, such as
567 Silhouette Score, and Calinski-Harabasz Index (Rousseeuw, 1987; Caliński and Harabasz, 1974) Finally, the
568 experimental datasets used in this study are completely labeled. In the future, an augmented approach can
569 be developed which will work well when the data is partially labeled. We hope that future work following
570 the aforementioned directions would concentrate on additional in-depth aspects of the proposed approach in
571 a more granular way.

572 7 Conclusion

573 In this study, we present a graph-theoretic approach for assessing data quality in classification tasks. This
574 study addresses a critical need for effective measures that connect model performance with data character-
575 istics. We propose a new index for quantifying the intrinsic separations between classes in data. Through

576 experiments on datasets from finance, medical, and marketing domains, we validated the effectiveness of
577 the proposed index against the widely used Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI). The proposed index enables de-
578 termination of feature importance and exhibits superior correlation with classification performance thereby
579 demonstrating its utility in multi-class datasets. These findings underscore the practical relevance of the
580 measure, offering new avenues for data quality assessment, enhancing classifier design and performance eval-
581 uation. This study contributes in two important ways. First, it establishes a reliable and generalizable
582 measure for data quality assessment. Second, by demonstrating the potential of proposed approach to ad-
583 vance classification tasks across diverse domains. Our empirical studies show that the insights on the class
584 separations can be used to shed light on several important aspects such as the amount of money saved by
585 detecting fraudulent transactions, the amount of money lost by missing the detection of fraudulent trans-
586 actions, and learning the feature importance. A key advantage of the proposed approach pertains to its
587 application in the pre-modeling phase which can offer explanations about a model’s performance without
588 even building the model. This study enriches the toolkit for data quality assessment and contributes towards
589 building more effective AI systems.

590 8 Appendix

591 8.1 Davies Bouldin Index

592 Let us have a set of points in \mathcal{R}^n and let C_i be a cluster of datapoints. We consider \mathbf{x}_j to be a datapoint
593 belonging to cluster C_i . We assume that we will carry out the computations in Euclidean space. We denote
594 the n -dimensional cluster center of C_i with A_i and the cardinality of C_i (number of points in C_i) to be T_i .
595 The within cluster distance between the points of a cluster, C_i is denoted with S_i .

$$S_i = \frac{1}{T_i} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{T_i} \|\mathbf{x}_j - A_i\|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

596 We denote the separation between clusters C_i and C_j with $M_{i,j}$.

$$M_{i,j} = \|(A_i - A_j)^2\|^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

597 Let $R_{i,j}$ be a measure of evaluating the vitality of clustering scheme. This measure will depend on two things
598 — i] S_i , within cluster distance of C_i for all the clusters — this has to be as low as possible and, ii] $M_{i,j}$,
599 the separation between two different clusters C_i and C_j — this has to be as high as possible.
600 $R_{i,j}$ is defined in terms of S_i and $M_{i,j}$ as follows.

$$R_{i,j} = \frac{S_i + S_j}{M_{i,j}} \quad (6)$$

601 This formulation satisfies the following conditions:

- 602 i] $R_{i,j} \geq 0$.
- 603 ii] $R_{i,j} = R_{j,i}$.
- 604 iii] When $S_j \geq S_k$ and $M_{i,j} = M_{i,k}$, we get $R_{i,j} \geq R_{i,k}$.
- 605 iv] When $S_j = S_k$ and $M_{i,j} \leq M_{i,k}$, we get $R_{i,j} \geq R_{i,k}$.

606
607 Lower the value of $R_{i,j}$, better is the separation between clusters C_i and C_j . On the contrary, a
608 higher value of $R_{i,j}$ indicates increased similarity between the clusters. When the number of clusters
609 obtained in a dataset is more than 2, the highest similarity score for a cluster (with respect to another
610 cluster) is taken into account.

$$D_i = \max_{j \neq i} R_{i,j} \quad (7)$$

611 Davies Bouldin Index (DBI) is the cumulative sum of D_i over all clusters in a given dataset. It shows that
612 the overall similarity or overlap of the clusters. Lower the value of DB, more separated are the clusters. For

613 a dataset with N clusters, DB is defined as follows.

$$DBI = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N D_i \tag{8}$$

614 The correctness of DBI in rendering class overlap is dependent on a stringent assumption stated as follows.
615 The cluster centers have to be distinct from each other and should possess a substantial amount of separation.
616 If the separation is less, DBI will not be indicative of the overlap present in the data. When the classes
617 originate from different cluster centers, DB works well in measuring the overlap between them.

618 8.2 Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree

619 The Euclidean minimum spanning tree (EMST) is a minimum spanning tree (MST) of a set of n points
620 in \mathcal{R}^d , where the weight of an edge between each pair of points is the *euclidean distance* between the two
621 points. An EMST connects a set of points using edges such that the total weight of the edges is minimized
622 and each point is reachable from any other point through the edges.

623 For EMST construction, it is assumed that we have a complete graph for a set of n points. The edge weight
624 between any two points is their euclidean distance. Hence, we have a graph $G(V, E)$ where V is the vertex
625 set, the set of points in \mathcal{R}^d and E denotes the edge set. EMST is a sub-graph H of G ($H \subset G$) in terms of
626 edges satisfying the following two conditions. Let e_H be the total weight of edges in H .

- 627 i] A vertex v of H is reachable from another vertex u of H , $\forall u, v \in H$.
- 628 ii] We satisfy condition (i) and the sum of edge weights of H , e_H is minimum.

629 8.3 Mathematical foundation of the EMST-based class-overlap index

630 Once we form the EMST from n points in a feature space, we have a connected graph of n vertices. A key
631 characteristic of EMST (and also a MST) is — the points are connected in the most compact fashion by
632 virtue of minimizing the total edge weights. The connection weight (or the edge-weight) between any two
points indicate their proximity. The task that we are addressing in this work is quantifying the degree of

Figure 3: This figure shows the minimum spanning tree (MST) for 15 arbitrary points. The datapoints belong to class 1 (indicated by red) or class 2 (indicated by green). When the two vertices of an edge belong to the same class, it is termed a *homogeneous edge* (the blue colored edges in the given figure). On the other hand, when the two vertices on edge belong to two different classes, we term it a *heterogeneous edge* (AB, BC, CF, and ED in the given figure.)

633 class-overlap in a dataset. Two aspects of an EMST are particularly interesting and can serve as a data
634 mine in this regard, they are — i] the class of the two vertices connecting an edge, and, ii] the weight of
635 that edge. Intuitively, in a dataset with well separated classes (low overlap), the edges of an EMST will be
636 mostly formed between vertices belonging to the same class, which are termed as *homogeneous edges*. An
637

edge whose two vertices belong to different classes is known as *heterogeneous edge* (Figure 3). Since EMST is a connected graph, we will indeed have at least one *heterogeneous edge*.

8.4 Mathematical properties of EMSTOI

EMSTO renders an overlap value between 0 and ∞ for a dataset. Such an extended and unlimited range can come in the way of proper comprehension of overlap existing in a dataset, and while comparing the class overlaps in two different datasets. Motivated to address this concern, we tweaked the calculation to restrict the overlap quantification in $[0, 1]$ in the following manner.

$$\text{EMSTOI} = \frac{\text{EMSTO}}{\text{EMSTO} + 1} \quad (9)$$

The function $f(x) = \frac{x}{x+1}$ is strictly increasing as $f(x_1) < f(x_2) \quad \forall x_1 < x_2$ in the domain of f . The strictly increasing property can be verified by obtaining its derivative and applying the quotient rule in the following manner.

We compute its derivative as follows:

$$f'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{x}{x+1} \right)$$

Applying the quotient rule, $\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{u}{v} \right) = \frac{u'v - uv'}{v^2}$, where $u = x$ and $v = x + 1$:

$$f'(x) = \frac{(1)(x+1) - (x)(1)}{(x+1)^2} = \frac{x+1-x}{(x+1)^2} = \frac{1}{(x+1)^2}$$

We may note that,

1. $f'(x) = \frac{1}{(x+1)^2}$ is positive for all $x > -1$, including $[0, \infty)$.
2. A positive derivative affirms strictly increasing nature of the function.

Hence, the order of EMSTO values is preserved in EMSTOI. The least value of EMSTOI (0) is obtained when EMSTO is 0. When EMSTO= ∞ , we get EMSTOI value of 1 which can be deduced through L'Hospital's Rule (Taylor, 1952).

8.5 Definition of the evaluating metrics

- **Accuracy** (Han et al., 2001) score computes the fraction of correctly classified instances (transactions). The higher the accuracy score, better is the classification performance, the computed value ranges from 0 and 1 (both inclusive). We define *accuracy* as follows:

$$\text{accuracy} = \frac{\text{number of correct predictions}}{\text{total number of points}} \quad (10)$$

- **Minority class F_1** (Han et al., 2001) is dependent on the correctness of the prediction of the datapoints belonging to the minority class (fraudulent transactions). Let N be the total number of data points and let the points in the dataset belong to only one of the two classes, class 1 (minority class) and class 0 (majority class). Let *True Positive (TP)* denote the number of datapoints correctly

666 classified to class 1 (minority class, fraudulent class). Similarly, *True Negative (TN)* denotes the
667 number of datapoints correctly classified to class 0 (majority class, authentic transactions). *False*
668 *Positive (FP)* denotes the number of datapoints belonging to class 0 (negative or majority) but
669 have been classified as class 1 (positive or minority) by the model (predicted as fraudulent, but
670 actually authentic). Similarly, *False Negative (FN)* denotes the number of datapoints belonging to
671 class 1 (positive or minority) but have been classified as class 0 (negative or majority) by the model
672 (predicted as authentic, but actually fraudulent).

673 Hence, $N = TP + TN + FP + FN$

674 Precision (for the minority or the fraudulent class) is the number of points correctly classified as a
675 minority (fraudulent transaction) scaled by the total number of minority predictions (including the
676 predictions misclassified as fraudulent).

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (11)$$

677 Recall (for the minority or the fraudulent class) is the number of points correctly classified as a
678 minority (fraudulent transaction) scaled by the total number of fraudulent transactions present in
679 the data (including the predictions misclassified as authentic).

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (12)$$

680 Minority class F_1 is the harmonic mean of the *precision* and *recall* for the minority class. It indicates
681 the fidelity of the classifier’s decision in the context of the minority class (fraudulent class in this
682 experiment). The higher the value of this metric, the better the performance. The computed value
683 lies between 0 and 1.

$$\text{Minority class } F_1 = \frac{2 * \text{precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (13)$$

684 8.6 Definition of the metrics assessing the correlation

685 • **Pearson correlation coefficient, $P(X,Y)$ (Han et al., 2001)**: Technically, it is the ratio of the
686 covariance of the two variables and the product of the variances of the variables. Let X and Y be
687 the two variables. Let σ_X and σ_Y denote the variances of X and Y respectively. We denote the
688 covariance of X and Y with $cov(X,Y)$.

$$P(X,Y) = \frac{cov(X,Y)}{\sigma_X * \sigma_Y} \quad (14)$$

689 • **Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient, $SP(X,Y)$ (Han et al., 2001)**: In essence, it is
690 similar to the previous metric. However, the key difference is, instead of considering the values,
691 Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient works on the rank of the values. Let X and Y be the two
692 variables for which we want to compute the correlation. Let $R(X)$ and $R(Y)$ be the ranks of the
693 items of X and Y . Let $\sigma_{R(X)}$ and $\sigma_{R(Y)}$ denote the variances of $R(X)$ and $R(Y)$ respectively. We
694 denote the covariance of $R(X)$ and $R(Y)$ with $cov(R(X),R(Y))$.

$$SP(X,Y) = \frac{cov(R(X),R(Y))}{\sigma_{R(X)} * \sigma_{R(Y)}} \quad (15)$$

695 9 Declarations

696 • **Availability of supporting data-** On request.

697 • **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests-**None.

- 698 • **Ethics approval**-Not Applicable. This article does not contain any studies with human participants
699 or animals performed by any of the authors.
- 700 • **Consent to participate**-Not Applicable.
- 701 • **Consent to publication**-Granted.
- 702 • **Generative AI**- Not used.
- 703 • **Authors' contribution**-
704 *Payel Sadhukhan* - conceptualization, implementing, writing
705 *Samrat Gupta* - conceptualization, implementing, writing, supervision
706
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